

Participation of Indian Women in Electoral Process

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Abstract:

This Women's participation in electoral process is a corner stone for democratic representation and gender equality. Despite global progress women remain under represented in political institutions and barriers like social and cultural norms, limited access to resources, illiteracy, financial constraints etc. impede their participation. Constitutional provision for equality to right, seat reservation, capacity building initiative, International commitments, removal of barriers, technology and financial supports are some measures taken to promote women's participation in electoral process. Today Indian women have moved beyond mere symbolic roles to become powerful influences in shaping electoral results. This has been possible with the support of women centred policies which empowering them as decision makers and change makers.

Introduction:

Women constitute slightly more than half of the world population. The participation of women and their engagement in the electoral process is an important marker of the maturity and efficacy of democracy in any country. Women's participation in the electoral process is a key indicator of Democratic health. It refers to women's involvement in voter registration and voting, standing as candidates, campaign management and political activism, holding public office and policy influences and decision making, at all levels of governance.

Voter registration and voting are the foundation of Democratic participation. Standing as candidates transform women from voters to decision makers. It is a crucial dimension of women's political empowerment beyond just voting. Women's participation in campaign management and political activism expands their role from voters and candidates to strategists, mobilizers, opinion leaders and change makers in

democracy. Campaign management and political activism are powerful avenues for women to shape political discourse of public policy. Holding elected office means serving as an officially elected representative in legislative and executive positions at local state or national level. It transforms women from participants to policy makers. Policy influences and decision making refers to women's active role in shaping laws, public policies, budgets and governance priorities, after entering political institutions. It moves women's participation from representation to real power. Women's participation in elections is not just about numbers but about voice, power and policy impact. Research across democracy shows that greater female representation leads to stronger welfare policies and community development outcomes.

In India women's participation in the electoral process is generally lower than men, either because they have been socialized differently as far as marriage, motherhood,

employment and property ownership and fewer resources. Therefore, present study was undertaken to know

i) the need of women's participation in electoral process, ii) barriers to women's effective participation in the electoral process and iii) strategies to overcome the barriers to women's participation in electoral process.

Need of Women's Participation in Electoral Process:

Women's participation in electoral process had following benefits:

1. Promotes gender equality: women's political participation is a fundamental prerequisite for gender equality and genuine democracy. Women's participation in politics is important to achieve sustainable development goal 5 which is to achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls and ensure women's full and effective participation and equal opportunities to leadership at all levels of decision making in political, economic and public life.

2. Addressing women's specific issues: Higher numbers of women in Parliament generally contribute to stronger attention to women's issues. Female politicians often raise issues like reproductive rights, domestic violence laws, maternal healthcare, education for girls etc. to get the policy attention. This ensures appropriate policy responses to address women specific issues and introduce women's sensitive measures.

3. Change of stereotypes: enhanced electoral participation and representation helps in cooperation with the women's movement and the media to change the stereotype image of women as only home makers to change it to law makers.

4. Improvement of economic performance and infrastructure: According to UN University women legislators improve the economic performance of their constituencies.

Countries with higher female representation show lower levels of corruption and higher economic growth.

5. Accountability and gender sensitive governance: electoral participation of women facilitates direct engagement in public decision making and is a means of ensuring Bator accountability to women. It helps in undertaking reforms that can help make all elected officials more effective at promoting gender equality in public policy and ensuring their implementation.

6. Enhances social benefits: When women are politically empowered economies tend to benefit. Closing gender gaps in employment including political leadership helps to increase global GDP.

Barriers To Women's Participation In Electoral Process:

Women in politics face various significant barriers which are as follows ...

1. Discrimination: Though the Indian constitution promotes gender equality, discrimination continues to be a wide -spread barrier to women's electoral participation. Women are less encouraged to run for official election than men. Discriminatory attitudes manifest in the limitations presented to Indian women including low access to information and resources. Women receive information mostly from men. Women are responsible for the majority of house work and child care which hinders them from entry in politics. Indian women are having less opportunities to get involved in organisations to gain leadership skills. Party leaders generally prefer to promote male rather than female candidates. There is a general bias in the thinking regarding winnability of female candidates preventing them from selecting women leaders for election.

2. illiteracy: literacy can play a key role in the dignification and independence of women in politics. Percentage of illiteracy found more in

women than men. Illiteracy limits the ability of women to understand the political system and issues, ability to move outside the home, ability to meet and collaborate with others. Many studies found that illiterate women are persistently mocked and devalued in the panchayat.

3.Finances: financial condition of women significantly affects their political participation in India. Women, especially in rural areas, mostly financially depend upon their families. Financial constraints can hinder women from participating in political activities as they may need to focus on earning a livelihood to support their families. Additionally, the lack of financial resources can prevent women from accessing necessary training and information related to political involvement.

4.Proxy representation: it is where women elected to office were largely controlled by the male family members. This is particularly prevalent in the local self-government and dubbed as “Sarpanch Pati”.

5.Social and cultural barriers: patriarchal norms and deep-rooted social beliefs often restrict women's participation in public life. Family responsibilities and lack of support hinders the women's participation in the electoral process.

6.Violence and intimidation: political violence and intimidation especially during elections disproportionately affect women candidates. The election commission of India has reported increasing cases of Cyber harassment and trolling targeting women in politics.

Strategies to Overcome The Barriers:

Several strategies have been made to overcome the barriers and to promote women's participation in the electoral. process.

1. Reservation in representation: the 73rd and 74th amendment to the constitution provided for reservation of 1/3 of the total number of seats for women in Panchayat Raj institutions and urban local bodies.

Women's Reservation Act 2023 mandates 33% reservation for women in Lok Sabha and state assembly.

Every registered political party should be legally obliged to give one third of the total number of party tickets distributed at every election to women. The representation of People Act 1950 will have to be amended to enable this strategy .

2.Capacity building initiatives: the National Commission for Women and civil society organisations have launched training programs at equipping women with leadership skills. Continuous training programs and mentorship for women in politics can build confidence and equip them with necessary skills for governance.

3.International commitments: India is a signatory to the convention on the elimination of all forms of discrimination against women (CEDAW) and aligns with the Beijing declaration on gender equality promoting women's participation in public life.

4.Removal of barriers: better educational opportunities for women improved financial stability and the relative erosion of social prejudices can enhance their political participation.

5.Promoting gender sensitisation: political parties and civil society must advocate for gender sensitization programs to break societal stereotypes and encourage equal participation of women in governance.

6.Technological and financial support: providing women with access to digital tools for campaigning and communication along with financial assistance or subsidies for electoral campaigns can help to overcome structural barriers.

Conclusion:

The term electoral participation in compasses a broad range of activities through

which individuals engage with political processes. These include the right to vote, contest elections, join political parties, engage in political activism, influence public policy and cultivate political consciousness. For women political participation is not only a matter of Democratic right but also key pathway to achieving gender equality and social empowerment.

Women's participation in electoral process is largely influenced by social and cultural barriers such as discrimination, illiteracy, financial challenges and violence etc.

Several measures have been taken to promote women's participation in electoral process including constitution provision for equality to right, seat reservation, capacity building initiative, International commitments, removing barriers, technology and financial support aimed at enhancing womens political representation.

Promoting electoral participation is an important way of improving state accountability and responsiveness and empowering the poor.

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